

Reaction of rice cultivars to gall midge attack in Orissa

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Rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* is a serious pest in the wet season, but activity is also observed in the dry season in areas receiving perennial flow irrigation. Varieties in the coastal tract appear to differ in level of susceptibility from varieties in the inland districts.

A trial in the 1980 and 1981 wet seasons at three representative sites — Bhubaneswar (Pun district), Rampur (Bolangir district), and Chakuli (Sambalpur district) — studied cultivar reactions to variable insect population pressure. The trial had 6 donor cultivars, 5 resistant varieties, 8 promising cultivars, and 3 susceptible checks grown in a completely randomized block design replicated 3 times with 100 hills/replication. Silvershoot infestation was measured at 55 days after transplanting.

Siam 29 and Eswarkora exhibited higher levels of silvershoot incidence at all three sites in both years (see table). Infestation level in Leuang 152, Ptb 18, and Ptb 21 was less than 1%. Resistant

Reaction of rice cultivars to gall midge infestation at 3 locations in Orissa, India, 1980 and 1981.

Cultivar	Parents	Av silvershoots (%) at 55 DT ^a		
		Bhubaneswar (Puri)	Rampur (Bolangir)	Chakuli (Sambalpur)
<i>Donors</i>				
Eswarkora		1.10	3.34	2.89
Leuang 152		0.00	0.07	0.24
Ptb 18		0.03	1.10	0.55
Ptb 21		0.00	0.19	0.19
Siam 29		5.69	7.28	10.18
W1263		1.10	1.08	0.60
<i>Resistant varieties</i>				
Kakatiya	IR8/W1263	4.95	2.30	4.29
Shakti	Ptb 18/Ptb 21//IR8	1.21	3.24	1.99
Phalguna	IR8/Siam 29	0.41	1.40	0.46
Surekha	IR8/Siam 29	0.38	1.40	1.04
Samlei	IR8/Leuang 152	0.16	0.26	0.07
<i>Promising cultivars</i>				
ORSJR-214	IRI/Leuang 152	0.36	0.96	0.71
OR127-3	RPW 6-13/Hema	0.00	0.06	0.00
ORI40-9-3	RPW 6-13/CR94-MR 1550	0.00	0.15	0.55
ORI32-3-1	Rajeswari/CR57	0.13	0.33	0.89
CR199-1	RPW 6-1 3/Supriya	0.07	0.00	0.13
CR401-6	Vijaya/CR94-15 12-6	0.95	1.29	1.47
CR404-24	CR94-1512-6/Pusa 2-21	0.10	0.00	0.06
RP8-9	IR8/W1257	10.19	13.08	4.46
<i>Susceptible checks</i>				
Jaya	TN1/T141	13.40	23.26	22.32
IET5656	RPW 6-13/Sona	16.76	12.78	16.42
RP356-112-1-1	IR8/Siam 29//Ptb 18/Ptb 21	17.10	18.07	8.19

^aMean of 3 replications. DT = days after transplanting.

variety Kakatiya had high infestation at all three sites. Shakti had high level of infestation only at Rampur. RP8-9 had high infestation at all three sites.

Infestation in susceptible varieties was very high. Variability in level of infesta-

tion among donors, resistant varieties, promising cultivars, and susceptible checks with respect to test sites was very low. Fluctuations in silvershoot incidence were mostly ascribable to environmental influences. ■

Effect of nitrogen fertilizer levels and spacing on rice gall midge and leaf-folder damage

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The effect of four nitrogen levels and three plant spacings on rice pest damage was studied in a field trial at Tirur during the samba season, July-August to November-December 1979-80. The two-factor experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Thirty-day-old seedlings of IR8 were planted in 9-m² plots with 50 kg P₂O₅/ha and 50 kg K₂O/ha. The crop

Effect of nitrogen fertilizer and spacing on gall midge and leaffolder damage at Tirur, India, 1979-80 samba.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Gall midge silvershoots (%)				Leaffolder-damaged leaves (%)			
	10 x 10 cm	20 x 20 cm	30 x 30 cm	Av	10 x 10 cm	20 x 20 cm	30 x 30 cm	Av
0	11.2	8.8	7.9	9.3	24.4	20.2	18.7	21.1
75	14.0	11.0	10.8	11.9	48.3	29.1	23.3	33.6
150	15.2	10.3	10.5	12.0	48.0	30.8	24.8	34.0
225	14.8	12.2	10.7	12.0	47.4	37.6	31.9	39.0
Av	13.8	10.5	10.0		42.0	29.4	24.7	
CD for N level				2.37				6.81
CD for spacing				2.05				5.90
CD for interaction				4.12				11.81

received no insect protection.

Gall midge damage was measured as the number of silvershoots to total tillers on 50 hills/ plot at 60 days after transplanting (DT). Leaffolder damage was measured as the number of leaves damaged to total leaves on 25 hills/plot at

75 DT.

Damage by gall midges and leaf-folders was rather high and increased significantly when nitrogen was added to the plot (see table). Damage also increased significantly at closer spacings. ■